

Modern Friedel-Crafts Chemistry. Part-XVII. Studies on the Acid-catalysed Dehydration of 3-(α -Naphthylmethyl)-3-pentanol, 2-(α -Naphthyl)-1,1-diphenyl-1-ethanol and 2-Methyl-2-(α -naphthyl)-2-butanol

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The title α -naphthylalkanols were prepared by unequivocal methods and their dehydration pattern was examined in the presence of both Lewis and Brønsted-Lowry acid-catalysts. 3-(α -Naphthylmethyl)-3-pentanol (5) gave acyclidehydration mixture of 1,1-diethylacenaphthene (10, mainly) and 2-ethyl-1-methyl-2,3-dihydrophenalene (11) with $\text{AlCl}_3/\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2$, and an acyclidehydration mixture of 2-methyl-1-(α -naphthyl)-1-butene (12) and *Z*- and *E*-3-(α -naphthylmethyl)-2-pentene (13) with 85% H_2SO_4 , PPA or NaHSO_4 . 2-(α -Naphthyl)-1,1-diphenyl-1-ethanol (6) gave 1-(α -naphthyl)-2,2-diphenylethene (16) with H_2SO_4 , PPA, NaHSO_4 , but a different unidentified product with $\text{AlCl}_3/\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2$. Finally, 3-methyl-2-(α -naphthyl)-2-butanol (7) gave 1,1,2-trimethyl-acenaphthene (18) with $\text{AlCl}_3/\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2$ but 2-methyl-3-(α -naphthyl)-2-butene (19) with 85% H_2SO_4 or NaHSO_4 . Both reactants and products were characterised by elemental, spectral, chemical and glpc analysis. Mechanistic interpretations have been given in terms of carbocation reactions and rearrangements.

In a preceding paper of this series, we reported a facile approach to the synthesis of 1,1-dimethyl- and 1,1,2-trimethylacenaphthenes through Friedel-Crafts cyclialkylation of α -naphthylalkanols 1 and 2.

The results were rationalised in terms of direct carbocation closure in the case 1 but rearranged carbocation closure in the case of 2. In continuation of our interest in Friedel-Crafts cyclialkylations in general and their application to the synthesis of acenaphthenes in particular, we report here on the utilisation of α -naphthylalkanols (5–7) as possible precursors for the synthesis of diethyl-, diphenyl- and trimethylacenaphthenes, respectively. As pointed out before¹, acenaphthenes have been found to be associated with diverse industrial and biological applications.

Results and Discussion

The α -naphthylalkanols under investigation, were prepared by the Grignard method. Accordingly, carbinols 5 and 6 were prepared by allowing ethyl α -naphthylacetate to react once with a little over two equivalents of ethylmagnesium iodide and once more with a little over two equivalents of

phenylmagnesium iodide followed by decomposition with a saturated ammonium chloride solution.

On the other hand, carbinol 7 was obtained from a reaction of α -naphthylmagnesium bromide with one equivalent of isopropyl methyl ketone followed by decomposition with a saturated ammonium chloride solution.

It is to be pointed out that attempted purification of the carbinols (5–7) by either distillation or column chromatography (over silica gel or alumina) resulted either partially or completely in elimination of water. Accordingly, the crude α -naphthylalkanols, whose identity and purity (over 95%) were ascertained by elemental and spectral ir and pmr

analyses, were taken directly to the next step. At this point however, some interesting observations about the pmr spectra of alcohols 5 and 7 are worthy to mention. While alcohols 5 showed pairs of partially resolved triplets and quartets for CH_2 and CH_3 respectively, alcohol 7 showed two distinct doublets for the two isopropyl methyl groups. These facts imply that hindered $(\text{ET})_2(\text{OH})\text{C}-\text{CH}_2\text{Ar}$ and $(\text{Me})_2\text{CH}-\text{C}(\text{Me})\text{Ar}$ rotations cause alcohols 5 and 7 to spend most (if not all) of their time in the form of the most stable conformers, namely (A) and (B). As a result, both the two ethyls of 5 and the two methyls of 7 will be magnetically nonequivalent and hence will have different but close chemical shifts². Experimental support for this view was found in the fact that when the pmr spectra of 7 was recorded at higher temperatures (50, 100 and 120°), the chemical shift difference (ΔV) between the two methyl doublets diminished gradually until it appeared eventually as a triplet at 120°. Understandably, increasing temperatures will allow sufficient energy to overcome the rotational barrier.

Dehydration behaviour of carbinols (5–7) under the influence of acid catalysts: The mode of dehydration of the carbinols showed great dependence on the type of acidic catalyst employed. On one hand, reactions induced by the Lewis acid catalyst $\text{AlCl}_3/\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2$ enhanced Friedel-Crafts cyclialkylation resulting in ring closure products; that dehydration mode is denoted *cyclidehydration*. On the other hand, reactions induced by protonic acids such as concentrated H_2SO_4 , polyphosphoric acid (PPA) or NaHSO_4 favoured side-chain dehydration to yield olefinic products. For consistency, this mode will be denoted *acyclidehydration*. These findings will become more evident when we consider individual cases below.

Dehydration behaviour of 3-(α -naphthylmethyl)-3-pentanol (5): On treatment with $\text{AlCl}_3/\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2$ catalyst, this carbinol gave 74% yield of a dehydration product. Combined ir, pmr and glpc data indicated this product to be a cyclidehydration mixture consisting of 1,1-diethylacenaphthene (10; 74%) and 2-ethyl-1-methyl-2,3-dihydrophenalene (11; 26%). As in Scheme 1, these two products are suggested to result from a direct tertiary carbocation closure via 8 to a five-membered ring and a rearranged secondary carbocation closure via 9 to a six-membered ring.

Scheme 1

The dehydration of carbinol 5 was also induced by other acidic reagents, namely, concentrated H_2SO_4 , PPA and NaHSO_4 . These reagents resulted in acyclidehydration to give hydrocarbon products whose olefinic nature was established through positive unsaturation tests. Careful analysis of these products by ir, pmr and glpc revealed that they are mixtures composed of the Saytzeff elimination product 2-ethyl-1-(α -naphthyl)-1-butene (12) and its Hofman counterparts *cis*- and/or *trans*-2-(α -naphthylmethyl)-2-pentene (13) in ratios approximating 3 : 1 with H_2SO_4 and 1 : 1 with PPA or NaHSO_4 .

Dehydration behaviour of 2-(α -naphthyl)-1,1-diphenyl-1-ethanol (6): The dehydration of this carbinol was induced by a number of acidic reagents including 85–95% H_2SO_4 , PPA, $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}$, NaHSO_4 and $\text{AlCl}_3/\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2$. Far from expectation, none of these reagents resulted in cyclidehydration to yield, 1,1-diphenylacenaphthene (17). Instead, the first four reagents induced direct acyclidehydration resulting in the formation of 1-(α -naphthyl)-2,2-diphenylethene (16). The product with $\text{AlCl}_3/\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2$ was different however, but its exact nature is still a subject of continued research. The results with carbinol 6 are formulated in Scheme 2.

As suggested in Scheme 2, regardless of the type of acid catalyst used, the first step invariably involves protonation of the carbinol to give oxonium ion 14. In the presence of the protonic acid catalysts H_2SO_4 , PPA, $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}$ and NaHSO_4 however, 14 undergoes a conjugate base-assisted one-step elimination of water and a proton

through species 15 (path-A) to give alkene 16. The failure of carbinol 6 to cyclise to 1,1-diphenylacenaphthene 17 via path-B is undoubtedly due to the unfavourable peri-interaction developing between the two phenyl groups and the hydrogen on the 8-position. However, research is currently underway to further support this view.

Scheme 2

Dehydration behaviour of 3-methyl-2-(α -naphthyl)-2-butanol (7): The dehydration of this alcohol was induced by both Lewis and Brønsted-Lowry acid catalysts. With $\text{AlCl}_3/\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2$ catalyst in petroleum ether solvent, this alcohol underwent rearranged cyclodehydration to form 1,1,3-trimethylacenaphthene (18; Scheme 3). This reaction introduces one more facile approach to the synthesis of compound 18 from readily available materials¹. The carbocation processes involved in the transformation of 7 to 18 are formulated in Scheme 3.

Scheme 3

Alcohol 7 was also dehydrated with both concentrated H_2SO_4 and anhydrous NaHSO_4 . In contrast to $\text{AlCl}_3/\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2$, the product with these two catalysts was shown to be the acyclidehydration

product 2-methyl-3-(α -naphthyl)-2-butene (19) resulting from Saytzeff elimination of water.

Experimental

All melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. In most cases, solids were purified by recrystallisation and liquids by column chromatography on silica gel (60–100 mesh). The purity and identity of the compounds were determined by spectral, elemental, glpc and tic analyses. ^1H nmr spectra (CCl_4 , unless specified otherwise) were recorded on a Varian EM-390 spectrometer (90 MHz) and ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 1320 spectrophotometer. The glpc data were recorded on a Varian 3700 instrument with vistadata using 10% carbowax 20 M (2 m) and 15% OV 275 (2 m). Microanalyses were performed on a Perkin-Elmer 240-13 analyser by the Microanalytical Unit of the Chemistry Department at KAAU. All the analytical samples were routinely dried over P_2O_5 for 24 h under reduced pressure.

The carbinols (5–7): Since attempts to purify these carbinols either by column chromatography on alumina or by vacuum distillation resulted in partial or complete dehydration to alkenes, the fairly pure crudes were taken directly to the next steps.

3-(α -Naphthylmethyl)-3-pentanol (5): A solution of methyl α -naphthylacetate (20 g, 0.1 mol) in dry ether (*ca* 30 ml) was added dropwise to the Grignard reagent prepared from magnesium turnings (5.04 g, 0.21 g-atom) and iodoethane (32.6 g, 0.21 mol) in dry ether (*ca* 100 ml).

Decomposition of the product by saturated ammonium chloride followed by separation of the organic layer, drying over anhydrous sodium sulphate and evaporation of the solvent left the crude alcohol (16.2 g, 71%) in the form of yellowish viscous oil (Found: C, 84.21; H, 8.20. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}$ calcd. for: C, 84.21; H, 8.77%); ν_{max} (neat) 3580 and 3480 cm^{-1} (OH); δ 0.87 (6H, br t, $2 \times \text{CH}_3$), 1.07 (1H, br s, OH, exchanged with D_2O shake), 1.1–1.7 (4H, a pair of partially resolved quartets, 2CH_2), 3.13 (2H, s, CH_2) and 7.2–8.23 (7H, m, ArH).

2-(α -Naphthyl)-1,1-diphenyl-1-ethanol (6): The procedure was exactly similar to that used for alcohol 5 with the exception that iodobenzene (42.84 g, 0.21 mol) was used instead of iodoethane. The crude alcohol was obtained in the form of

yellowish viscous oil (20 g, 62%) (Found : C, 86.38 ; H, 5.93. $C_{24}H_{20}O$ calcd. for : C, 88.88 ; H, 6.17%) ; ν_{\max} (neat) 3 560 with a shoulder at 3 580 cm^{-1} (OH) ; δ (CCl_4) 2.1 (1H, br s, OH, exchanged with D_2O shake), 3.95 (2H, s, CH_2) and 6.6—7.8 (17H, m, ArH).

3-Methyl-2-(α -naphthyl)-2-butanol (7) : A solution of 3-methyl-2-butanone (8.6 g, 0.1 mol) in dry ether (30 ml) was added dropwise to the Grignard reagent prepared from α -bromonaphthalene (20.7 g, 0.1 mol) and magnesium turnings (2.4 g, 0.1 g-atom) in dry ether (50 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 h, decomposed by saturated ammonium chloride then the ether layer was separated and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Evaporation of solvent ether left the desired alcohol in the form of yellowish viscous oil (14.6 g, 68.4%) (Found : C, 82.23 ; H, 7.74. $C_{15}H_{18}O$ calcd. for : C, 84.11 ; H, 8.41%) ; ν_{\max} (neat) 3 580 and 3 490 cm^{-1} (OH) ; δ ($CHCl_3$) 0.6 (3H, d, J 6 Hz, $CHCH_3$), 1.95 (1H, br s, OH, exchanged with D_2O shake), 2.75 (1H, q, $CHMe_2$), 7.4 (4H, m, ArH), 7.75 (2H, m, ArH) and 8.75 (1H, m, ArH).

Acid-catalysed dehydration of the alcohols (5–7).
General procedure : The procedures described earlier for cyclidehydration of arylalkanols with $AlCl_3/CH_3NO_2$ ^{1,3,4} and concentrated H_2SO_4 ^{1,3,5} and for dehydration of arylalkanols with anhydrous $NaHSO_4$ were essentially followed. However, the following aspects were considered : (i) in $AlCl_3/CH_3NO_2$ -catalysed reactions, the amounts of reactants were alcohol (0.05 mol), $AlCl_3$ (0.06 mol), CH_3NO_2 (0.6 mol) and petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) (5 ml g^{-1} of alcohol), (ii) in H_2SO_4 -catalysed reactions the amounts were alcohol (0.05 mol), 85% H_2SO_4 (1 ml g^{-1} of alcohol), petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) (5 ml g^{-1} of alcohol), (iii) in $NaHSO_4$ -catalysed dehydrations, a mixture of alcohol (2 g) and $NaHSO_4$ (5 g) was heated with occasional stirring at 160° on a sand-bath for 3 h, the reaction mixture was then poured over ice-cold water (30 ml), extracted with ether, the ether layer was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent was evaporated to obtain the dehydrated product and (iv) in polyphosphoric acid (PPA)-catalysed reactions, a mixture of the alcohol (2 g) and PPA (6 g) was heated on a water-bath for 2 h with occasional stirring, left to stand overnight and then the mixture was poured on to ice-cold water (50 ml), the organic product extracted with ether, washed with water, dried over sodium sulphate and the solvent was evaporated.

The products obtained from these dehydration reactions were purified by column chromatography and subjected to elemental, ir, pmr and glpc analyses. Besides, they were examined for unsaturation by reaction with Br_2 and $KMnO_4$. A summary of the products and their analysis is given in Table I.

TABLE I—PRODUCTS OF REACTIONS OF α -NAPHTHYLALKANOLS (5–7) WITH ACID CATALYSTS^a

Sl. no.	Catalyst	Yield ^b %	Product ^c (yield %)
<i>A. Products from 3-(α-naphthylmethyl)-3-pentanol (5)</i>			
1d	$AlCl_3/CH_3NO_2$	73	1,1-Diethylacenaphthene (10 ; 74), 1-Methyl-2-ethyl-2,3-dihydrophenalene (11 ; 26)
2e,f	85% H_2SO_4	71	2-Ethyl-1-(α -naphthyl)-1-butene (12 ; 50), 3-(α -naphthylmethyl)-2-pentene ((Z)-13, 50)
3e,f	PPA	73	12 (40), (Z)- and (E)-13, (60)
4e,f	$NaHSO_4$	71	12 (37), (Z)- and (E)-13 (63)
<i>(B) Products from 2-(α-naphthyl)-1,1-diphenyl-1-ethanol (6)</i>			
5g	$AlCl_3/CH_3NO_2$	74	Unidentified
6h	85% H_2SO_4	69	1-(α -Naphthyl)-2,2-diphenylethene (16 ; 100)
7h	PPA	71	16 (100)
8h	$NaHSO_4$	66	16 (100)
<i>(C) Products from 3-methyl-2-(α-naphthyl)-2-butanol (7)</i>			
9i	$AlCl_3/CH_3NO_2$	41	1,1,2-Trimethylacenaphthene (18 ; 100)
10i	85% H_2SO_4	51	2-Methyl-3-(α -naphthyl)-2-butene (19 ; 100)
11i	$NaHSO_4$	56	19 (100)

^aAll products gave satisfactory C and H analysis. ^bMole per cent of product hydrocarbons based on original arylalkanol. ^cThe percentage composition of various products was determined from careful analysis of ir, pmr and glpc data. ^dThe products from this reaction showed no sign of unsaturation as it did not decolourise bromine or $KMnO_4$ solution. Its ir spectrum showed the absence of OH. Its pmr spectrum (CCl_4) showed aromatic and aliphatic protons in a ratio of 1 : 2 and revealed the following signals : a large triplet centered at δ 1.03 for CH_2CH_3 protons of 10, two much smaller overlapping triplets centered at δ 1.73 for CH_2CH_3 of geometrical isomers of 11 and a sharp singlet at δ 3.50 for CH_2 of 10 ; other peaks appeared mainly between δ 1.2 and 2.4 and to a much lesser extent between δ 3.1 to 4.0 but their interference did not allow proper assignment to respective protons. ^e(i) The olefinic nature of the products from these reactions was established by positive unsaturation response, by the disappearance of the OH band from the ir spectra and by the presence of vinylic proton signals at δ 4.8–5.7 6.6 in the pmr spectra. ^fThe pmr spectra of these products showed aromatic and aliphatic protons in a ratio of 1 : 2. Besides, these pmr spectra showed the following explicable signals in varying proportions : a set of triplets located between δ 0.8 and 1.33 for CH_2CH_3 of 12 and 13, one pair of doublets centered at δ 1.55 and 1.71 for $=CHCH_3$ of geometrical isomers of 13, an apparent pair of quartets located between δ 1.8 and 2.5 for CH_2CH_3 of 12 and 13, a doublet at δ 3.77 and a singlet at δ 3.95 for CH_2Ar in (Z)- and (E)-isomers of 13 respectively, a singlet at δ 6.5 for $=CH-$ in 12 and a multiplet at δ 7.0–8.1 for aromatic protons in 12 and/or 13. ^gThis product gave positive unsaturation tests. Their pmr spectra showed a multiplet at δ 6.7–7.8 for both aromatic and vinylic protons. ^hProducts 18 and 19 were identical in all respects to the same ones obtained in earlier work¹.

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